

WP 5 : DEVELOP & EXECUTE

Deliverable 5.3 [Demonstrator]

Templates and Data Collection
and Visualisation Instruments

Work Package	WP 5
Deliverable	D5.3 Templates and Data Collection and Visualisation Instruments
Lead Partner	ZSI
Month Due	M34
Month Submitted	M34
Deliverable Type	Demonstrator
Dissemination Level	Public
Lead Author	Christian Voigt (ZSI)
Contributors	Science Gallery at Trinity College Dublin (IE), Kersnikova (SI), Ars Electronica (AT), ZSI (AT)
Reviewer(s)	Ana Smerdu (Kersnikova), Frank Vloet (WAAG)

Revision History

Rev	Date	Author	Partner	Description
0.1	05/09/2019	Christian Voigt	ZSI	Concept presentation
0.2	30/09/2019	Partner Team	KI	Implementation pilot 1 (Kersnikova), Feedback
0.3	05/10/2020	Team ZSI	ZSI	Initial draft
0.4	31/01/2021	Partner Team	TCD	Implementation pilot 2 (TCD), Feedback
0.5	23/02/2021	Frank Vloet Ana Smerdu	Waag KI	Reviewers Comments
1.0	25/02/2021	Christian Voigt	ZSI	Final draft
2.0	02/03/2021	Christian Voigt	ZSI	Addition of chapter on 'Limitations & Robustness'

Learning from Observations: The Observation Mapper

Glossary of Terms

Acronym	Definition
GPS	Global Positioning System
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
STEAM	Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics
CSV file	Comma Separated Values file type
GIS	Geographical Information Systems
GPIOs	General Purpose Input/Output pins

Table of Contents

Introduction	7
The Observation Mapper.....	7
How does it work from a pedagogical perspective?.....	9
Who is it for?	10
How was it developed?	10
What defines the observation mapper?.....	14
Suggested scenarios.....	15
Tips for Starting Point 1: Data Collection.....	16
Tips for Starting Point 2: Data Exploration.....	19
Tips for Starting Point 3: Device Building	23
Limitations and Robustness	26
Summary and Conclusion.....	28
Annexes	30
Annex A: List of materials	30
Annex B: Software tool chain	31
Annex C: List of available pins for sensor extensions	33
Annex D: Visualising GPS Data on Google Maps	34

List of Figures

Figure 1: The observation mapper and its functions.....	8
Figure 2: A map of overflowing rubbish bins and polluted green spaces.....	9
Figure 3: Core building blocks of the observation mapper (Sept 2019)	11
Figure 4: User story mapping.....	12
Figure 5: STEAM activities involving a maker space	14
Figure 6: Assembling the observation mapper in Ljubljana (Jan 2021)	15
Figure 7: User guidance on the observation mapper.....	18
Figure 8: Local data overview	18
Figure 9: Breadboard version versus PCB (Printed Circuit Board) version	23
Figure 10: Electronics design using Fritzing Software.....	24
Figure 11: Openly accessible files for 3d- printing	25
Figure 12: Parametrised design of the casing.....	25
Figure 13: Data Glitch	26
Figure 13: Required software libraries	31

List of Tables

Table 1: Activities per user group, including potential benefits	11
Table 2: Overview of visualisation instruments.....	20
Table 3: Use of GPIOs.....	33

Introduction

The SySTEM2020 project has set out to generate an in-depth look at science learning in the non-formal sector, designing a toolkit of frameworks, tools, and practices for the evaluation of non-formal science education programmes. The goal is to enable learners to evaluate their own learning under a number of different metrics including their engagement with a topic, e.g. by formulating or implementing research activities such as data collection. Additionally, reflection can include data such as the time spent on certain activities. This type of self-reflection by learners leads to a valuable metacognition around science learning, which can have implications for the students' interest and achievement in formal education. Hence, the 'observation mapper' represents a part of the SySTEM 2020 Platform for self-evaluation by students during activities providing science learning outside the classroom (other parts are learning portfolios, credentialisation and self-assessment).

The observation mapper is a device for exploring ways to make data collection part of reflective sense making, through learning analytics and data visualisation. Primarily, the device is designed to support informal learners in tracking their activities and to present them in an appealing way on an outward facing website. However, understanding the role of data privacy is a major task, therefore we opted for producing visualisations locally. There is also the option of making the visualisations available to the outside world, potentially as part of learning portfolios.

The Observation Mapper

This report is a step-by-step guide explaining the making of an 'observation mapper' so that young people and organisations can build their own device and integrate data collection into their workshops. The device shown below (Figure 1) is one version to get started, but can be modified, depending on the available 'maker skills' among workshop participants.

The device aims to give as much feedback as possible during the data collection process, and therefore includes a small screen, providing information on how many points have been mapped and whether the signal strength is sufficient to record GPS positions. The device also tracks the path a person is walking while mapping and indicates whether collected data can be accessed through a web-browser, which simultaneously offers an option to download the collected data for further processing on a local device. At no time does data need to be uploaded to the Internet, meaning that data are entirely under

the control of the device holder. There is one exception to this: if data shall be visualised in an advanced way (i.e., including data filtering, map styling and heat map visualisation), this can be achieved through a locally running python notebook or, since installing a python notebook can be challenging without prior experience, a similar notebook can be accessed online, in which case the data are uploaded to a server¹.

Figure 1: The observation mapper and its functions

To give an example of how the device can be used, we looked at a hypothetical relationship between rubbish bins and increased pollution of green spots nearby. To test this hypothesis we chose two categories: Category 1 for an overflowing rubbish bin and Category 2 for polluted green spots. Once the data are downloaded, Categories 1 and 2 can be replaced by appropriate icons and displayed on a map together with the path the mapping person recorded (see the dotted blue line in Figure 2, below). What seems a straightforward process, can turn out to be more complicated in reality, as it raises the question of whether any piece of paper (no matter how small) justifies mapping an area as polluted. Nonetheless, understanding the need to specify and possibly standardise data collection can become a desirable part of the learning experience.

¹ For the piloting of the observation mapper, informed consent was obtained for using the mapping data of pilot participants. Still, at its core, these are lists of GPS coordinates at specific times and no connection to a particular person is visible.

Figure 2: A map of overflowing rubbish bins and polluted green spaces

How does it work from a pedagogical perspective?

This section discusses the link between our everyday observations, the way we learn informally and why ‘mapping observations’ can help to make learning more interesting or more related to our daily experiences.

A pedagogical foundation for the development of the mapper gadget is to enable a better understanding of how our observations create, shape and extend our mental models. Mental models are heuristics that help us to make sense of the things we observe without investing a lot of time or cognitive effort². We use our mental models more or less consciously and their levels of details can be more or less elaborated. For example, during times of Covid-19, wearing masks and keeping physical distances is proven to help society’s fight against increasing infection numbers. However, our decision as to where we should wear masks is partly influenced by our assumptions (mental model) about Covid-19 as an infectious disease (e.g. Does it spread in a train station or only in smaller, confined spaces? Does it matter how long we stay in one place? Should it be a specific type of mask? etc.). Additionally, our ‘mask wearing behaviour’ is also influenced by observing other people (e.g., politicians, peers, figures of authority). However, often we are overly influenced by what we have seen last or what impressed us most. In that sense we are rather bad in calculating averages over longer time spans or creating meaningful categorizations of our observations post-hoc. So being conscious of how our observations

² Gentner, D., & Stevens, A. L. (1983). *Mental models*. Erlbaum.

shape our assumptions and how we learn from our observations is a good starting point for designing ‘informal experiments’ or ‘explorative data journeys’ involving a DIY mapping device.

Who is it for?

The tool is for educators to share with their young learners and communities. It is also for learners who have already mastered the fundamentals of making, who want to put their skills into practice by building a gadget.

As part of SySTEM 2020, two partners (Kersnikova in Ljubljana and Science Gallery at Trinity College Dublin) piloted the gadget in the context of their informal science workshops and courses. The main idea was to connect what they learned during non-formal learning sessions with observations made outdoors, i.e. things participants could recognise in their surroundings.

How was it developed?

A few expectations have been set already in the task description:

- the device should be **modular**;
- there should be an option for **DIY**;
- there should be an option for adapting and modifying the functionality of the device or the **type of data** collected;
- data collected, such as the GPS coordinates, should be used in reflective and sense-making activities, supported by adequate **visualisations**;
- special care should be dedicated to the **privacy** of learners.

Yet, we also subscribed to a participatory design process, during which we present ideas, discuss possible features and priorities. Co-design was initiated first at a consortium level and then also in the context of the specific pilots in Ljubljana and Dublin.

The first discussion about the observation mapper took place during the Milan Practice Partner meeting in September 2019. During that occasion, core building blocks such as GPS as a common denominator for the data collection and Google Maps as an example for a lightweight data visualisation were introduced. However, at that time, the device had no protective casing yet and no working user interaction.

Figure 3: Core building blocks of the observation mapper (Sept 2019)

In a second step we already discussed high-level story lines about in what ways the observation mapper could be used and be beneficial. Protecting the ‘privacy’ of learners was one of the first features mentioned, as well as the option of guiding learners through data manipulation activities as part of learning through analysing data. Other activities, such as ‘intentionally sharing data with others’ have not yet been tested but remain a valid option for the future.

Table 1: Activities per user group, including potential benefits

Role	Activity	Goal / potential benefit
Learner	Accesses a save space for data submission and exploration	Protection of privacy
	Accesses and modifies data visualisations	Understanding the implications of data aggregation
	Shares data intentionally with selected groups	Gaining recognition
Facilitator	Supports learner activities on request	Coaching the learning process
	Browses anonymized data visualisations filtered by event	Obtains some evidence about the impact of a workshop beyond the on-site visitor feedback.
Visitor	Browses anonymized data visualisations (show cases)	Learns about informal learning offers of particular organisations
Accreditor	Reviews data profiles and provides feedback	Supports a process of recognition, based on negotiation

In preparation of the pilots in Ljubljana and Dublin we had six meetings with Kersnikova and five meetings with Science Gallery Dublin. Other partners also contributed with comments and recommendations, so we had two more workshops with Ars Electronica (Linz, AT) during 2020. The first session with each partner followed a user story mapping approach³ in order to canvass potential use cases, scenarios and necessary features.

Figure 4: User story mapping

However, before we addressed the process design, we discussed the following questions in order to better understand the opportunities and strategic implications that could come with the observation mapper.

- **What is the topic of the workshop / workshop series?**

This question was mostly discussed in the context of particular workshop plans held by the organisations piloting the ‘observation mapper’. In the case of Kersnikova we started with the idea of designing a series of 4 workshops around the topic of transforming an invasive plant (i.e. Japanese knotweed) into paper. For Dublin we had the starting idea of ‘exploring litter, living with plastic and the impact of bio-plastics’, which fitted well an ongoing exhibition⁴ at the time.

In Kersnikova, workshops on the topic of Japanese knotweed went ahead, categorising and visualising the knotweed plants. Unfortunately, the paper making part of workshop was not possible, since in person meetings were not allowed at the time.

Since the plastics exhibition in Science Gallery Dublin was already finished when the observation mapper was implemented, the workshops instead followed a new theme linked to a course⁵ being offered to students at the time, over the duration of a week.

³ Left side graphic by Patton, J. (2014). *User story mapping*. O’Reilly Media, Inc.

⁴ <https://dublin.sciencegallery.com/plastic>

⁵ <https://dublin.sciencegallery.com/news/apply-for-our-online-open-mind-programme-for-ty-students>

The theme was data, ethics and AI. One particular topic of interest was the element of bias in data influencing AI algorithms that rely on large amounts of data. By having two people mapping the same phenomenon, the plan was to compare and discuss circumstances that could lead to categorizing observations differently. Ultimately leading to different conclusions. The specific topic of the mapping journey was ‘emotional impressions’ in Dublin related to Covid-19. ‘Emotional impressions’ could include graffiti, decaying corners, empty shopping streets, people wearing masks etc.

- ***Who are the users? How would they be using the mapper?***

Under this question, we discussed primarily what existing skills the users have. For example, in the case of Ljubljana the engagement tracker was used with a group young learners who had experience of programming, which allowed us to use more advanced tooling for data analysis and visualisation (e.g. Python Notebooks and/or Binder⁶). In Dublin, users had a more diverse background, and no programming experience could be assumed, hence we stuck to Excel and Google Maps. In both cases, the important steps centred on participants discovering interesting ways of ‘questioning’ a set of data.

- ***Why would they want it? What problems would it solve?***

Firstly, it is important to consider all stakeholders in possible usage scenarios. Organisers and designers of informal learning workshops have an opportunity to embed learning in pre-or in-between workshop activities, which generate data. This opens up the opportunity to concentrate workshop activities on analytical or interpretative activities, whereas data collection activities need to be handled largely independently by workshop participants.

Secondly, actually building and adapting a data collection instrument, provides a unique opportunity to look into the design of research and experiments, understanding how many small-scale decisions make up the foundation of reliable and trustworthy results.

- ***If we build this product and it is successful, can it be sustained?***

All designs, schematics and programs are available as open-source materials, therefore, apart from the costs for hardware, sustaining the ongoing use of the ‘observation mapper’, as well as fine-tuning its functionality, is mainly a question of having personnel with the necessary skills to lead DIY workshops in a maker context.

⁶ <https://jupyter.org/binder>

Using the data from the SySTEM 2020 map⁷, we can see that approximately 10% of the 1500 activities mapped involve maker spaces. At least potentially, these activities could consider integrating parts of observation mapping, such as ‘building the mapper’ or ‘programming the mapper’ in their workshop activities. Depending on the advances we will see concerning ‘digitalisation in schools’, a ‘privacy preserving, multi-purpose data logger’ could also be of interest to formal education institutions.

Figure 5: STEAM activities involving a maker space

What defines the observation mapper?

The device aims to respond to a number of specific needs such as:

- *Variety of use scenarios:* Depending on the time available, the gadget can be used pre-built so that the focus is on using local data during coding sessions, visualising the data and their positions in bar charts and maps respectively. Alternatively, parts can be organised and assembled during a session, which is recommended in cases where the gadget will be modified or extended later.
- *Moderate price point for components used:* The observation mapper components cost a total of approximately €30. Components can also be reused in many different scenarios.
- *Modular design and extensibility:* Based on open-source software, the mapper’s functionality can be extended by choosing from a wide range of sensors, e.g.

⁷ <https://system2020.education/the-map/>

measuring air quality through parts per million (PPM) or understanding urban weather through measuring the temperature of heat islands in densely built-up areas (see Annex C – for a list of pins available for additional sensors). At the moment only the GPS sensor is a fixed component, since this is the underlying meta-data, needed to pin an observation on the map.

- *Privacy respecting use:* There is no central learning management system and the data collected are not uploaded to the Internet at any time. Hence, the activities of young learners (where and when they collect their data) are kept private. In times when our data power the algorithms of tech giants, mapping can contribute to an awareness of how much data we generate by simply carrying around smart phones with integrated GPS sensors.

However, the most important ingredient to ‘learning from observations’ is not the technology but an overarching story, motivating young learners to be curious and explore relationships between observations, data and insights.

Suggested scenarios

Due to Covid-19 regulations during the SySTEM 2020 project, it was not possible to organise outdoor observations in small groups as originally planned. However, workshop facilitators could still map observations in their respective cities (Ljubljana and Dublin) and provide these local datasets to workshop participants, who then explored, visualised and analysed the data and the underlying phenomena in online workshops.

Figure 6: Assembling the observation mapper in Ljubljana (Jan 2021)

However, it is preferable to involve the young learners directly in the process of soldering the data collection device and collecting the data outdoors. This effect was confirmed by the first pilot, who worked with the data first and then built the gadget during a follow up workshop (Figure 6, above).

On a modular basis, there are three ‘starting points’, where workshops can start to make use of the ‘observation mapper’. Each starting point allows for a different focus and could be offered in isolation if observation mapping devices are already available or data had been collected beforehand (as it was the case for our two online workshops in Ljubljana and Dublin).

Starting Point 1: Data Collection

Starting Point 2: Data Exploration

Starting Point 3: Device Building (Hardware Assembly, Programming, 3D-Printing)

Below, each starting point scenario is described in more detail.

Tips for Starting Point 1: Data Collection

Data collection depends widely on the initial workshop planning, clarifying the depth of understanding to be achieved through concrete workshop activities. Workshop objectives will depend on the length of the workshop, diversity of participants, prior knowledge of workshop participants as well as the experience of workshop facilitators.

Workshop context in Ljubljana: Starting from the idea that specific plants can be used for paper production, a workshop was designed around the Japanese knotweed plant, which is an invasive, dominant plant but can also be harvested for paper production. Mapped observations were then related to the positions of knotweed plants and their respective shapes (young plant, fully evolved plant, dying plant). Using these visualisations in combination with photos of plants could deepen the learning about where ‘invasiveness’ is visible and what plants are available at a specific time of the year (e.g., for paper making workshops).

Workshop context in Dublin: The overarching theme of the workshop week in Dublin was AI, Ethics and Data. In a first brainstorming session, we discussed how AI usually uses data sets with millions of entries, aggregating the data from thousands of persons. Even

though this is not a situation we could recreate using the observation mapper, we found that a comparison between two data sources would be an interesting scenario on a micro level, helping to understand how possible biases or differences during the data collection process could influence the overall meaning of the data. Hence, two people mapped observations of cultural expressions related to Covid-19 walking through the city of Dublin (rating categories: Bad, OK, Good, Excellent). The mapping experiment yielded a number of insights, such as ‘Who mapped how much’, ‘Did the two mappers have distinct mapping profiles, e.g. being more moderate or extreme in their ratings’ etc.

Apart from the workshop context, i.e. relating a topic of interest (e.g. plants, urban culture) with observations that can be rated, we found a number of ‘rules of thumb’ to prepare data collections efficiently.

- I. Ensure that the phenomenon you want to map, can be actually observed (e.g. ‘Is the state of a plant sufficiently distinguishable?’ or when looking for inter-rater differences, ‘Are mappers observing similar areas and phenomena?’).
- II. Concerning the categories: Are the categories sufficiently different? Do the categories capture most of the variations likely to be observed?
- III. Data analysis benefits from a minimum of data points. Can the mapping include at least 40 locations? For example, if we were to map decaying houses, newly built areas will have a very limited observation potential.
- IV. Given that we place observations on a map, does the position of the observed phenomenon play a role? For example, mapping people who wear or don't wear masks may not be very meaningful on a map. However, mapping small shops, bus or subway stations could make sense, if we were interested in knowing to what degree public spaces comply with Covid-19 rules (masks and social distancing guidelines).
- V. Regardless of how thorough your preparation ‘practice best reflection’, that is try to test your mapping concept before rolling it out to a larger group.

The data collection process itself is straight forward and activities during the data collection process can be separated into ‘mapping’ and ‘monitoring’.

Mapping: After starting the mapper (see Figure 7 below), screen one shows for 2 seconds followed by screen two, indicating that the device is ready to map. If the user is in front of the phenomenon to be mapped, she/he can enter a mapping category as indicated on screen three.

Monitoring: Once a learner has been mapping for a while, she/he can check the statistics of how many locations have been mapped (screen four). In both pilots, more than 100 locations were mapped. It is also possible to monitor the number of satellites the GPS is reaching to check for GPS accuracy. This is advisable in narrow streets, close to high buildings.

Figure 7: User guidance on the observation mapper

**SY
STEM
2020**

**SCIENCE
LEARNING
OUTSIDE
THECLASSROOM**

Learning paths outside the classroom: Explore and download your data, stored locally on your mapper

Paths you walked

Show 10 entries Search:

Date	CET Time	Raw Time	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude	Num of Sats	Sat Speed	Precision
121020	07:36:34	6363400	48.232141	16.371889	179.40	8	5.7782	1.20
121020	07:36:37	6363700	48.232097	16.371891	180.10	8	4.9078	1.20
121020	07:36:40	6364000	48.232055	16.371895	180.90	8	3.5373	1.20
121020	07:36:43	6364300	48.232020	16.371905	181.80	8	3.9448	1.20
121020	07:36:46	6364600	48.231981	16.371911	184.20	8	4.7596	1.20
121020	07:36:49	6364900	48.231958	16.371917	184.60	8	1.9816	1.20
121020	07:36:52	6365200	48.231948	16.371916	185.00	8	0.5556	1.20
121020	07:36:53	6365300	48.231945	16.371917	185.70	8	0.5000	1.20
121020	07:36:53	6365300	48.231945	16.371917	185.70	8	0.5000	1.20
121020	07:36:53	6365300	48.231945	16.371917	185.70	8	0.5000	1.20

Showing 1 to 10 of 500 entries
Previous 1 2 3 4 5 ... 50 Next

[Download as CSV](#)

Figure 8: Local data overview

As we can see in the upperpart of screen four (Figure 7), while categorising specific locations, the gadget has two more features that could run in parallel: tracking the path of the user (Path ON/OFF) and enabling on-the-spot checking of the collected data through the browser (Web is ON/OFF). ‘Web is ON’ creates an access point (similar to a WiFi hot

spot) which any mobile device can access. Screen five gives a reminder of the access point's name ('Mapper') as well as the URL that needs to be called in the browser (<http://44.44.44.44>).

Once the access point is running, we see a tabular overview of the spots mapped so far. Figure 8 shows all the points making up the path of the mapping person. We can see that path markers are taken every 3 seconds. In this case, we can also see a glitch at 07:36:53, when the same path marker has been recorded three times. Later on, the analysis will filter out duplicates, so that each data point is unique. We can get a similar overview of the points categorised and, since the table can be sorted by column, we can also get an approximate idea of how often each category has been used.

There is also a button for downloading the data as a CSV file, which can then be processed by several data exploration tools, as described in the next section.

Tips for Starting Point 2: Data Exploration

While there are many ways to learn from an analogue version of highlighting data on a map, manipulating data and displaying them on a map digitally can be even more effective. Put simply, digital versions allow for easy manipulation of visualisations regulating zoom-levels, colouring of markers, contextual information on the map or even aggregating markers to heatmaps, as we will see in a later example.

The variety of things we can manipulate in digital visualisations will depend on the time we can invest, either into making programming part of the workshop or into developing visualisations as a service to be developed upfront. Of course, also with limited resources, data from the observation mapper can be put on a map, e.g., by using google maps (see Annex D).

Table 2: Overview of visualisation instruments

	Visualisation Process	Visualisation App
Low Code / No Code	Excel & Google Maps ⁸ , Tableau ⁹ , Datawrapper ¹⁰	Streamlit ¹¹ & Pydeck hosted on Heroku (automated deployment) ¹²
Code	Python Jupyter Notebooks ¹³ , iPyLeaflet ¹⁴ , Kepler.gl ¹⁵	GeoDjango ¹⁶

As shown in Table 2, above, nine applications have been considered. Three of them were used during the two pilots in Ljubljana (Jupyter Notebooks) and in Dublin (Excel & Google Maps). The links in the footnotes refer to visualisations, using data from the observation mapper. The table also resembles a 2x2 matrix, differentiating between:

- **Visualisation Process vs Visualisation App:** A visualisation process is a step-by-step process leading to tables, charts and maps, where each step is executed manually. A visualisation app, however, executes many interim steps in the background and can run through multiple steps in a pre-defined manner. Also, a process solution is much more hands-on on the side of the workshop participants, requiring a deeper understanding of the technology, whereas the app would work as soon as data are provided and the necessary visualisation parameters are provided.
- **Code vs Low Code:** This is also a critical distinction in order to make observation mapping feasible for a diversity of workshop providers and participants. From a No-Code / Low Code perspective, participants can upload data to Google Maps and change icons or maps backgrounds. They would achieve similar visualisations with Tableau or Datawrapper, platforms which are also used for data-driven journalism or corporate reporting. The challenge here is the time needed to set up the tools and understand basic interactions. However, once these skills are mastered, much more fine-tuning is possible and entire dashboards can be composed⁹.

⁸https://www.google.com/maps/d/u/0/edit?hl=de&mid=1taoR_4y8R1C3x2F098ZelS1H_AvLS6G4&ll=48.22170424908103%2C16.375382499999994&z=15

⁹<https://public.tableau.com/profile/christian6183#!/vizhome/HeatmapVersionLjubljana/heatmapversion>

¹⁰ https://www.datawrapper.de/_/or7ei/

¹¹ <https://github.com/chrvoigt/observation-viz>

¹² <http://mapper.innodesign.education/>

¹³ https://github.com/chrvoigt/observation_analysis

¹⁴ <https://innodesign.io/ipyleaflet-interactive-maps-in-python/>

¹⁵ <https://innodesign.io/kepler-gl/>

¹⁶ <https://docs.djangoproject.com/en/3.1/ref/contrib/gis/z>

When developing an app, the ability to rapidly prototype and share an application saves time and developer resources. We briefly tried GeoDjango, which is a full-blown Python Web framework with GIS (Geographical Information Systems) support. However, providing the same features in Django as existed in the python notebooks required significant effort. Streamlit on the other hand, allowed us to reuse most of the code in the app, so that experiences made in ‘code-based’ visualisation workshops could be easily transferred into a ‘no-code’ visualisation app. Streamlit enables python notebooks to run in a browser and Heroku automates deployment, i.e. installing the Tornado web-framework required by Streamlit as well as the python libraries powering data analysis. The following screens present some of the current visualisations as implemented in the app (<http://mapper.innodesign.education/>)¹⁷. They are not meant to be self-explanatory but require knowledge of the mapping process and the meaning of the Categories 1-5.

Data Cleaning

If multiple rows have the same GPS coordinates, only the last one is kept.

Plausibility tests

Select a range of plausible distances between observations to be included:

Minimum distance is 0 meters and maximum distance is 500 meters. Your data are reduced by: 0.79 %. Using the slider, you can change these values and see the effect in the table below. There are 125 data rows now.

	time	latitude	longitude	distance	sats	precision	category
116	17:05:37	46.069719	14.525566	404.380000	10	0.880000	2
82	16:48:32	46.070672	14.523805	242.990000	9	0.910000	3
124	17:10:57	46.066862	14.526094	236.060000	10	1.150000	4
23	17:51:04	46.059694	14.513479	196.260000	9	1.150000	3
32	17:54:18	46.059717	14.511144	163.880000	9	0.990000	1
58	16:36:39	46.067700	14.521400	158.430000	7	1.290000	1
52	16:32:15	46.066439	14.521028	126.340000	7	1.280000	1

¹⁷ The current hosting can cause the app to be rather slow in responding (15 – 30 secs), but we are working on an improvement.

This bar chart shows the usage frequency per category.

This bar chart indicates the quality of your GPS coordinates. 5+ is good.

Pairwise comparison of mapping data

Tips for Starting Point 3: Device Building

Step 1: Getting all materials and tools ready, connecting the pieces and (optionally) soldering

Make sure you have all materials and tools needed. You will find a complete list of components in the Annex. In total, you can expect to pay approximately €30 for components.

For the experimental breadboard version (see image below, left), no tools are required. However, for a hard-wired version (see image below, right), a soldering iron, solder and a stripping pliers will be needed.

Figure 9: Breadboard version versus PCB (Printed Circuit Board) version

Figure 10: Electronics design using Fritzing Software¹⁸

The components must be connected according to Figure 10, above. There are three components that belong to the Wemos Mini Ecosystem (microcontroller, battery charger, display) and two more components which use I2C communication. The connections are shown by the green, yellow, red and black wires in Figure 10.

Step 2: Uploading the sketch and making (optional) adaptations

The sketch of the mapper can be found on Github, which makes sure that you get the latest version with improvements and bug fixes: <https://github.com/chrvoigt/observation-gadget>. Before you can upload the sketch to your DIY mapping device, you need to get your tool chain ready (see Annex B).

Step 3: 3D-Printing the casing

The casing can be 3D printed and the design is made openly available on two prominent websites:

- Thingiverse <https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:4664256>
- Wikifactory <https://wikifactory.com/@chrvoigt/mapper-casing>

¹⁸ <https://fritzing.org/>

Figure 11: Openly accessible files for 3d- printing

These archives include the original design files needed to make adaptations in Fusion360¹⁹, which has educational, free licences as well. The dimensions of the box can be easily adapted, so that workshops can print casings according to the size of their printed circuit boards (PCBs). Equally, the cut-out text – currently saying ‘STEM’ – can be replaced with another word as needed.

Figure 12: Parametrised design of the casing²⁰

¹⁹ <https://www.autodesk.com/products/fusion-360/personal>

²⁰ <https://www.autodesk.com/products/fusion-360/blog/parametric-modeling-in-fusion-360-tutorial/>

Li mi t a t i o n s a n d R o b u s t n e s s

Collecting data can take effort. For one, it is the time taken to walk around and it is also the cognitive effort needed to do the actual categorisation of observations. In addition, depending on whether one remembers the mapping itinerary, it might even be impossible to generate the same data twice. Hence, losing data at this stage should be avoided.

Based on the initial piloting of the observation mapper. We describe two scenarios where data could be destroyed: (a) data storage runs out of flash memory²¹ and (b) the micro-processor gets less than the required 2.8 Volts during a writing process.

Memory limitations

We did run a few tests with about 10.000 data entries during path tracking. If we capture GPS coordinates at a rate of 4 secs, this corresponds to 666 minutes (or \approx 11 hrs). At this point we would suggest transferring the data to a laptop for example and delete the flash memory²². An associated challenge could also be a glitch during the data generation / writing process. These glitches would lead to an error messages when loading the webpage, but ideally the page would still finish loading and data could be downloaded (see Figure below for a data glitch).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Date	Time	RawTime	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude	Sats	SatSpeed
2	121020	07:12:47	6124700	48.231100	16.375006	160.20	4	0.5926
3	121020	07:12:47	6124700	48.231100	16.375006	160.20	4	0.5926
4	160.20	4	0.5926	18780			
5	121020	07:12:47	6124700	48.231100	16.375006	160.20	4	0.5926

Figure 13: Data Glitch

Power consumption

Using an Ammeter we can see that the observation mapper draws between 150 – 170 milliampere. Powering the device with a LiPo battery of 1,000 mA/h we get between 3 and 4 hours running time. However, power consumption is influenced by temperature as well as how the observation mapper is used. For example, if we don't track the entire mapping path (i.e., writing GPS coordinates every 4 secs) and just map single locations, running time will increase.

²¹ <https://learn.adafruit.com/memories-of-an-arduino/arduino-memories>

²² Flash memory is subject to wear and tear, i.e., the substance holding the information 'leaks' after many thousands of writings, depending on temperature, magnetic fields, chemical or mechanical impact. However, for prototyping purposes this should not matter. See also <https://cybergibbons.com/uncategorized/arduino-misconceptions-5-youll-wear-out-the-flash-memory/>

There is still a potential to optimize power consumption, which would require testing varying use scenarios (e.g., varying the use of path tracking and web monitoring²³) under different conditions (e.g., outside temperatures). For now, we recommend starting with a fully charged device to get the envisioned 3-4 hours.

At the moment, there is no mechanism that would shut down the device when battery power is too low. This can lead to the path file being corrupted, i.e., made unreadable. However, this flaw hasn't been observed with the ratings, which stayed intact. Still, to increase the robustness of the observation mapper, a solution will be available when switching to the maker hawk micro-board²⁴, which has an integrated lithium battery management system. Or alternatively, a larger battery of about 2000 mAh would also add to the running time of the device.

²³ There is no definitive number that defines the power consumption of individual components, e.g., an OLED display uses more or less power, depending on the number of pixels used. However various ball-park figures can serve as orientation (WEMOS wit access point \approx 70 mA, GPS module \approx 45 mA, OLED \approx 20 mA).

²⁴ Product description: <https://www.makerhawk.com/products/makerhawk-esp32-development-board-wifi-with-0-96inch-oled-display-wifi-kit32-arduino-compatible-cp2012-for-arduino-nodemcu>

Summary and Conclusion

In summary, we can say that starting with an already concrete notion of how the observation mapper could work, the development of the device went through a number of iterations. Conceptual as well as technical improvements were made along the way.

Summary of findings:

- *Heterogeneity of groups & support needs:* Even though the first pilot was targeted at computer literate youths, their skills naturally differed at an individual level. Bringing every workshop participant along, especially when technical problems arise, can be quite challenging in an online environment. Encouraging peer learning, i.e. helping each other in break-out rooms, could be an option, otherwise all the action relies on the workshop facilitator.
- *Installation troubles, reliability and speed of cloud services:* During the first workshop we relied on locally installed visualisation environments. While this approach can work out of the box, there are many reasons why a learners' device might have issues: such as the age of the computer or a particular configuration which isn't compatible. However, especially in times of Covid-19, it's not possible to convene all workshop participants in a computer lab where organizers have full control over the learning environment. Therefore, we looked into several cloud services such as Google's Collab, which allows for online collaboration in python notebooks. However, these settings have specific use conditions in that either the length of sessions or the maximum number of participants is restricted. Also, because it's a free service, there is no control over the quality of service, i.e., if many were using the service, the service could slow down or freeze. So, in the end, local installations seemed preferable, especially since programming was an intended part of the workshops.
- *Importance of building and mapping:* Right from the beginning, our intention was to get science learning out of any specific corner (literally speaking), be it chemists' lab or computer scientists' virtual world. Covid-19 disturbed these plans to some extent, but not entirely. For safety reasons, instead of the entire group, only workshop facilitators could go out and map a relationship (self-invented or requested by the group). Looking at data and knowing about its history made a difference. But particularly in the first workshop, participants volunteered to trial the mapper after the workshop and later on there was a workshop where people would build and flash their own gadgets. We would conclude that building your

own self-sufficient machine has its appeal and can therefore be a motivational force for engaging with technology.

- *Be ready to improvise:* The device uses off the shelf components at a moderate price point. DIY has the benefit of being able to replace parts that don't work. However, there is also a risk of the device breaking more easily than comparable gadgets which are mass produced. In some instance we had parts loosening or soldering points becoming unresponsive. We would present that as an opportunity to look for fixes. For example, when a battery charger broke, it was replaced by use of a power-bank; when some touchpoints became unresponsive, rather than undoing the wiring, we changed the programming diverting the most essential features to the remaining touch points, keeping the device usable; last but not least, during the second pilot, the device crashed after 1.5 hrs of data collection, still the data could be saved from the device before flashing it with a new version of code.

Learning from examples and encouraging experimentation

The observation mapper developed in SySTEM 2020 is a first prototype. Future work could extend didactical scenarios. For example, while developing the observation mapper, we sometimes underestimated the novelty of the approach. Building your own learning device is not yet standard in schools, so participants were quite happy to go with pre-designed experiments to see whether they could replicate the results (e.g., learners using the mapper after the workshop in Ljubljana continued to map knotweed plants, even though they could have opted for a different mapping topic).

On the other hand, actively asking learners to choose potential mapping topics can cause issues since the topics chosen may not relate directly to science learning. For example, towards the end of the Dublin workshop, participants were asked what they would choose to map if it could be anything. The range of answers were: scenic areas, safe spaces, places where Irish language is seen, nice beaches, birds, places with trees, street art, murals, chalk drawings of children etc.

While it may not be immediately clear how these topics could be embedded in science learning, or what the relationships for mapping categories are, it provides an opportunity to start with topics that young learners are concerned with, and then work to understand where the importance of these topics comes from and how it can be related to science that has an impact on people's daily experiences.

Annexes

Annex A: List of materials

Important: Any links to buying options should not be seen as an endorsement and we have no benefit from any purchases made through the links or in any other web-shop. Link have been included as a useful starting point, as you can then compare details and prices.

1. MPR121²⁵ Capacitive Touch Sensor ≈ €3
2. Wemos D1 (ESP8266) ≈ €5
3. OLED²⁶ Shield ≈ €5
4. Battery²⁷ charger ≈ €3
5. PCB Prototyping shield ≈ €1
6. NEO-6M GPS²⁸ ≈ €6
7. LiPo Battery ≈ €5
8. Breadboard for testing
9. Wires

Total: ≈ €30

There is an option to replace the Wemos D1 by the MakerHawk ESP8266 WiFi Development Board (≈ €10), including charger, microboard and OLED all in one. This could bring down the cost to €25, while making the hardware more compact.

²⁵ <https://electronics.semaf.at/MPR121-Capacitive-Touch-Sensor-Breakout-Board>

²⁶ <https://electronics.semaf.at/OLED-066-Shield-for-Wemos-D1-Mini-Board>

²⁷ <https://www.amazon.de/gp/product/B08GM2W6PM>

²⁸ <https://www.amazon.de/gp/product/B07V6C5J7P/>

Annex B: Software tool chain

1. Install the Arduino IDE²⁹ for your operating system (Windows, MacOS, Linux)
2. if you use Windows, you need to install a driver (CH430):
 - a. Download site: https://www.wemos.cc/en/latest/ch340_driver.html
 - b. A description with screenshots <https://www.dnatechindia.com/ch340g-drivers-download-installation-guide.html>
 - c. Restart your device
3. Install the ESP8266 board and associated libraries to your Arduino IDE. A pretty good description can be found here <https://randomnerdtutorials.com/how-to-install-esp8266-board-arduino-ide/>
4. Before flashing you might need to install a number of libraries, specially if you are using Arduino for the first time. However, the IDE will tell you if that is needed during the compilation process (see below the list of libraires used by the mapper). At the time of writing (January 2021) the sketch worked with the latest versions of all libraries.

```

GPS_Web | Arduino 1.8.13
GPS_Web Cap_touch.h Display.h GPS_UBlox.h SDCard.h Web.h
1 // date:
2
3 // third party libraries
4 #include <TinyGPS++.h> // Tiny GPS Plus Library
5 #include <SoftwareSerial.h> // Software Serial Library so we can us
6 #include <Wire.h> // I2C library
7 #include <Adafruit_GFX.h> // Graphic library
8 #include <Adafruit_SSD1306.h> // OLED library
9 #include <FS.h> // SPIFF file system
10 #include "Adafruit_MPR121.h" // Capacity touch library
  
```

Figure 14: Required software libraries

5. Unfortunately, one library needs to be installed manually. This is going to be improved in the future, but for now there is a process description <http://arduiniana.org/libraries/tinygpsplus/>
6. Next, we need an extension³⁰ of the Arduino IDE so that we can upload files to the files system. As a result, you should see a new entry under *Tools* saying

²⁹ <https://www.arduino.cc/en/software>

³⁰ <https://arduino-esp8266.readthedocs.io/en/latest/filesystem.html#uploading-files-to-file-system>

'ESP8266 Sketch Data Upload'

We need to upload two pieces of software:

- the sketch, this is how the program is called, that makes all pieces of hardware talk to each other;
- and a website, which allows us later to connect our smart phones or laptop directly to the mapping device in order to download the website that allows us to check our data on the go and finally download our data for further visualisation.

The folder you can download from Github, contains already a folder called 'data', there we included all files needed for displaying the website.

7. Finally, we need to resize the flash memory to provide sufficient space for the data we are going to collect. We recommend reserving 3 MB for the file system (FS).

Annex C: List of available pins for sensor extensions

Wemos ESP 8266 https://www.wemos.cc/en/latest/d1/d1_mini.html

Table 3: Use of GPIOs

Label on Wemos D1 (ESP 8266)	Used for ...	GPIO Number
TX, RX	Linked to Serial Commun.	1, 3
A0	Analogue Sensors	
D0	Not recommend **	16
D1	OLED	5
D2	OLED	4
D3	Sensors *	0
D4	Sensors *	2
D5	Sensors *	14
D6	GPS	12
D7	GPS	13
D8	Not recommend **	15

* e.g. a DHT22 sensor running on 3.3 V

**<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1pQuBocanzCZJ3KPUpu3VvpOOBzboqXDuwQDVP5UYcXc/edit#gid=0>

Comparison between ESP8266 and ESP32 <https://makeradvisor.com/esp32-vs-esp8266/>

Annex D: Visualising GPS Data on Google Maps

Download the Mapping locations

Download 4 files from <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1ELcxRb1u-b0pSX74evMmpiw1WiAN6U4?usp=sharing>

The first files we use are

- mapper_ca.csv
- mapper_cb.csv

'c' stands for 'categories'

'a' or 'b' stands for mapper A and mapper B respectively.

Login to Google

<https://accounts.google.com>

Google
Hi Christian
voigt.innovation@gmail.com
Enter your password
.....
 Show password
Forgot password?

Visit Google map creation

<https://www.google.com/maps/d/>

- click 'Owned'
- then 'CREATE A NEW MAP'

Add layer and import first CSV files (Mapper B)

- Click 'Import' (under Untitled layer)
- Upload first CSV File: **mapper_cb.csv**

After a successful upload you should see the following screen ...

Choose columns to position your placemarks

Select the columns from your file that tell us where to put placemarks on the map, such as addresses or latitude-longitude pairs. All columns will be imported.

- Date ?
- Time ?
- RawTime ?
- Latitude (latitude) ?
- Longitude (longitude) ?
- Altitude ?
- Sats ?
- SatSpeed ?

Continue Back Cancel

Click 'continue' and choose 'Category' as labels for your markers ...

Choose a column to title your markers

Pick a column to use as the title for the placemarks, such as the name of the location or person.

- Altitude ?
- Sats ?
- SatSpeed ?
- Precision ?
- Category ?
- Mapper ?
- Latitude_a ?
- Longitude_a ?

Finish Back Cancel

Import second CSV files (Mapper A)

- Click 'Add layer' and upload the second CSV file **mapper_ca.csv**
- Uncheck the suggested 'Latitude' and 'Longitude' fields
- This time choose 'Latitude_a' and 'Longitude_a' as geo-positions (you might need to specify which one is Latitude and Longitude (see yellow box))

After that you see the standard blobs in blue along the rivers (which we can change in a second)

Changing the layout

Changing the shape of the marker

- click on the bucket right to 'All items'

You will see some icons, but click on 'more options' and you see a wide range .. I recommend the simple dot, which helps with reading the labels later on ...

As you have probably already seen, in this section you can also change the colour of your markers ..

Adding a label

It would be good to see the categories beside each marker ...

For that click on 'uniform style' and you get the option to 'Set label', where you can choose 'Category' ...

Finally, you can also change the type of maps, using Satellite images.

